

PHOTOCHEMICAL FORMATION OF HYDROGEN PEROXIDE FROM WATER PART I. IN PRESENCE OF ZINC OXIDE

BY C. NARASIMHA CHARI AND M. QURESHI

The photochemical formation of hydrogen peroxide from water with zinc oxide as a sensitiser has been studied in detail both in sunlight as well as in artificial ultraviolet and visible light. The yield of hydrogen peroxide increases in presence of some organic compounds which presumably act as stabilisers. Of the nine organic substances employed for this purpose, phenol was found to be the best. An increase in the amount of zinc oxide produces a corresponding increase in the reaction rate which, however, tends to a limit with a constant intensity of light. An increase in the p_H has been found to increase the yield of hydrogen peroxide. The formation of hydrogen peroxide also takes place in the total light from a tungsten filament lamp as well as in the violet region of the visible spectrum isolated by means of filters, although in the latter case the reaction is very slow. This indicates that the photosensitive range of zinc oxide extends up to the violet.

The photosensitising activity of zinc oxide, prepared by different methods, has been studied and it has been found that zinc oxide, prepared from carbonate by ignition, has the greatest activity.

The photochemical formation of hydrogen peroxide from water, photosensitised by zinc oxide, has been studied by some workers in recent years. Baur and Neuweiler (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1927, **10**, 901) found that exposure of aqueous suspensions of zinc oxide in contact with air to sunlight results in the formation of hydrogen peroxide. They further observed that the yield of hydrogen peroxide considerably increased in the presence of small amounts glycerol, dextrose or benzidine, the latter substances being themselves oxidised at the same time. Gopala Rao and Dhar (*vide* "Chemical Action of Light" by N. R. Dhar, 1931, p. 263) found that hydrogen peroxide was formed in relatively great quantities on the addition of very small quantities of ethylamine, methylamine, phenol, acetone, alcohol, organic acids like acetic acid and benzoic acid and inorganic substances like sodium hydroxide. Dhar and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) also observed that cadmium oxide behaves just like zinc oxide. The formation of hydrogen peroxide from water in the presence of zinc oxide was confirmed by experiments carried out by Goodeve (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, **33**, 340). Yamafuji and Nishioeda (*Biochem. Z.*, 1938, **296**, 348; **298**, 293; 1939, **300**, 414; **303**, 260; **301**, 404; 1940, **305**, 354) observed that hydrogen peroxide was formed when aqueous solutions or suspensions of biological sensitisers, such as dried yeast extract, chlorophyll etc., were exposed to ultraviolet light, alone or in the presence of stabilisers. They believe that hydrogen peroxide is produced partly by the decomposition of water and partly by the photochemical auto-oxidation of the added substances. The object of the present investigation was to make a quantitative study of this reaction with a view to elucidating its mechanism.

EXPERIMENTAL

In the following work four samples of zinc oxide, prepared by different methods, have been employed. The first sample of zinc oxide was prepared by precipitating an aqueous solution of zinc nitrate while hot with a slight excess of sodium hydroxide solution. The precipitate was thoroughly washed until it was free from alkali and nitrate, dried, powdered and ignited at $\cdot 800^\circ$ in an electric furnace. It was then passed through 150 mesh and ignited

once again. Powdering, when necessary, was always carried out in an agate mortar. The colour of the oxide was slightly yellowish. Another sample of zinc oxide was prepared from zinc sulphate instead of zinc nitrate, by precipitation with alkali, the experimental procedure remaining the same as in the previous case. For the third sample, zinc carbonate was ignited at 400° in an electric oven for two hours. The resulting oxide was sieved and further ignited at 800° . The fourth sample of zinc oxide was prepared by igniting the nitrate at 350° . The colour of this sample was greenish yellow which persisted when the oxide was heated up to a temperature of about $1,000^{\circ}$ for two hours in air or up to a temperature of 400° for three hours in vacuum. Morse and White (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1892, **14**, 314) observed that oxygen and nitrous gases were tenaciously occluded by the oxide prepared by calcining the nitrate. A hot water extract of the oxide gave the test for nitrite. Small amounts of the nitrite could be leached out through repeated washing of the coloured oxide with boiling water but the colour did not altogether disappear even on prolonged washing extending over three days. All the chemicals employed in the preparation of the above samples were Merck's analytical reagents or extra-pure chemicals.

The source of illumination was a Heraeus quartz mercury vapour lamp mounted in a metallic box with a circular aperture in front and operated on 220 volt A.C. circuit in conjunction with a special transformer. The voltage between the electrodes of the mercury arc was maintained at 100 volts, the amperage being 3.5. The lamp was operated in a horizontal position parallel to the reaction vessel which was placed at a distance of 15 cm. from it. The arc length was about 5 cm.

The usual method for the estimation of hydrogen peroxide employing permanganate gives inaccurate results in the presence of organic substances which are added to stabilise hydrogen peroxide. The iodometric method is more suitable for the estimation of hydrogen peroxide in the presence of organic compounds, and hence this method as modified by Kolthoff was tried by us in the present investigation. Preliminary experiments, however, revealed that this method needed further modification, with regard to the concentration of the acid used, when, as in the present case, very small amounts of hydrogen peroxide are to be estimated. A series of estimations carried out with known solutions of hydrogen peroxide of low concentrations, using the quantities of the acid and potassium iodide given by Kolthoff, indicated that more iodine was liberated than what corresponded to the amount of hydrogen peroxide in the solution, on account of the oxidation of hydriodic acid by atmospheric oxygen. The procedure, finally adopted for carrying out the estimation, was as follows:—The solution, in which hydrogen peroxide was to be estimated, was made up to 50 c.c. and to this were added 0.5 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid (*d*, 1.84), 0.2 c.c. of a *N* solution of ammonium molybdate and 0.3 g. of potassium iodide. The solution, after being kept in the dark for about 10 minutes, was titrated against *N*/100-sodium thiosulphate solution, using a standardised microburette, after the addition of 2 c.c. of freshly prepared starch solution. No iodine was liberated in the absence of hydrogen peroxide with the concentrations of the acid and the iodide given above within 10 minutes.

In these experiments in which the light from a quartz mercury vapour lamp or sunlight was used for irradiating the solution, care had to be taken to prevent the photolysis of hydrogen peroxide formed during the reaction. It is well known that ultraviolet rays of short wave-length (250-300 $m\mu$) decompose solutions of hydrogen peroxide at a measurable rate. In order to prevent this simultaneous photodecomposition of hydrogen peroxide, it was

necessary to make use of a substance which would stabilise hydrogen peroxide in ultraviolet light. Anderson and Taylor (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 650, 1210) studied the inhibition of the photochemical decomposition of hydrogen peroxide solutions by various substances, both organic and inorganic, in ultraviolet light of different wave-length regions and came to the conclusion that phenol produced complete inhibition in the range 200–305 $m\mu$. Baur and Neuweiler (*loc. cit.*) noticed an increase in the yield of hydrogen peroxide when small amounts of organic substances were added to aqueous suspensions of zinc oxide, exposed to sunlight. Evidently, the increased yield is due to the inhibitory action exerted by these added substances on the photodecomposition of hydrogen peroxide formed in the reaction. In order to choose the best stabiliser for the present investigation, it was necessary to undertake a comparative study of the influence of the various organic substances, which have already been found to inhibit the thermal and photodecomposition of hydrogen peroxide. For this purpose, aqueous suspensions of zinc oxide, each containing 0.2 g. of the oxide in 30 c.c. of twice distilled conductivity water and an exact quantity of a stabiliser, sufficient to make the solution 0.1M with respect to it, were exposed in open pyrex flasks to sunlight. After a period of five hours all the flasks were removed at the same time. The contents of the flasks were filtered, the precipitates washed well and the hydrogen peroxide content of each was estimated according to the procedure already described. The results are shown in the following table in which *C* represents the amount of hydrogen peroxide formed in g. moles per litre.

TABLE I

Zinc oxide (c. p. Merck, 0.2 g.), conductivity water (30 c. c.), and stabiliser (0.1M)
exposed to sunlight for 5 hours.

Stabiliser ...	Phenol	Glycerol	Acetanilide	EtOH	Rt ₂ O	Acetone	Benzidine	Salicylic acid	Oxalic acid.
$C \times 10^6$...	57.30	44.30	42.85	30.60	19.55	14.60	6.45	4.45	0.55

It is evident from the above that phenol exerts the greatest stabilising effect on the reaction. The other substances are given in the decreasing order of efficiency. These results have been confirmed by repeating the experiments several times.

In the experiments described below phenol or glycerol was used as a stabiliser, the quantity used being such that the solution was always 0.1M with respect to it.

Effect of varying the amount of the Photosensitiser.—In these experiments, 30 c.c. of conductivity water containing varying amounts of zinc oxide (prepared from nitrate by precipitation) and a fixed amount of phenol were exposed to the total ultraviolet light from a mercury vapour lamp in a quartz flask for two hours.

TABLE II

Zinc oxide, conductivity water (30 c.c.) and phenol (0.1M) exposed to total
ultraviolet light for 2 hours.

Zinc oxide (g.)	0.01	0.03	0.05	0.10	0.20
$C \times 10^6$	0.38	0.79	1.07	1.10	1.10

The results, given above, indicate an increase in the amount of hydrogen peroxide with a corresponding increase in the quantity of the photosensitiser.

Influence of Time of Exposure.—In these experiments an aqueous suspension of zinc oxide containing phenol as a stabiliser was exposed for different periods of time to the light from a quartz mercury vapour lamp focussed by a glass condenser. The reaction vessel was a rectangular glass cell of 25 c.c. capacity with a tubular opening. The results are given in the following table.

TABLE III

Zinc oxide (prepared from nitrate, 0.1 g.), conductivity water (15 c.c.) and phenol (0.1M) exposed to light from a quartz mercury vapour lamp.

Time of exposure (hrs.)	...	2	4	6	8	10	12
$C \times 10^6$...	0.60	0.95	1.25	1.40	2.10	2.30

Experiments in Monochromatic light in the Visible Region.—The photochemical formation of hydrogen peroxide from water takes place in the presence of zinc oxide in sunlight. As sunlight also includes ultraviolet rays which are transmitted by glass, it was of interest to find out if zinc oxide is capable of bringing about this reaction in the visible light from which ultraviolet rays have been completely eliminated and if so which part of the visible light is concerned in this process. For this purpose experiments were carried out with monochromatic visible light, isolated by means of Wratten gelatine-glass filters. The source of light was a quartz mercury vapour lamp. Exposure to violet light (400–470 $m\mu$), for ten hours produced about 0.25×10^{-6} g. moles per litre of hydrogen peroxide, while in other parts of the visible spectrum, hydrogen peroxide could not be detected. This shows that the photosensitive range of zinc oxide extends up to 435 $m\mu$.

Effect of p_H .—In these experiments, the source of visible light was a 1000 watt tungsten filament lamp connected to 220 A. C. mains in series with a resistance and an ammeter and enclosed in a wooden box having a circular aperture in front. A high degree of intensity was secured by the use of a reflector. The reaction vessel which was a flat-bottomed pyrex flask of 50 c.c. capacity was placed at a distance of 37 cm. from the source of light. The heat rays were cut off by a hollow glass filter through which water was circulated. The light was brought to focus inside the reaction vessel by means of a glass condenser. The results of this experiment are summarised in the following table.

TABLE IV

ZnO (prepared from sulphate, 0.2 g.), aqueous solution of NaOH (30 c.c.) and glycerol exposed to light from a 1000 watt lamp for 5 hours.

NaOH (moles/litre)	...	Nil	0.005	0.01	0.017	0.05	0.083	0.167	0.33	0.50
$C \times 10^6$...	0.20	0.85	0.95	1.15	1.70	2.35	2.45	4.55	5.80

The above results indicate that in alkaline solution, the yield of hydrogen peroxide increases with an increase in p_H value.

Sensitising Action of different samples of Zinc Oxide.—The following experiments were performed to compare the sensitising activity of zinc oxide prepared by different methods mentioned above. The results are summarised in Tables V and VI. In these tables the letters C. I. indicate the sample prepared from carbonate by ignition, S. P. the sample prepared from sulphate by precipitation, N. P., the sample prepared from nitrate by precipitation and N. I., the sample prepared from nitrate by ignition.

TABLE VI

Zinc oxide (0.1 g.), conductivity water (15 c.c.) and phenol (0.1M) exposed to light from a quartz mercury vapour lamp focussed by a glass condenser for 2 hours.

ZnO	(C. I.)	(S. P.)	(N. P.)	(N. I.)
$C \times 10^6$	1.25	0.80	0.75	Traces

TABLE VII

Zinc oxide (0.2 g.), conductivity water (30 c.c.), and phenol (0.1M) exposed to light from 1000 watt lamp. for 5 hours.

ZnO	(C. I.)	(S. P.)	(N. P.)	(N. I.)
$C \times 10^6$	0.75	0.70	0.50	Traces

TABLE VIII

Zinc oxide (0.2 g.), conductivity water (30 c.c.) and phenol (0.1M) exposed in open pyrex flasks to sunlight for 5 hours.

ZnO	(C. I.)	(S. P.)	(N. P.)	(N. I.)	(S.P.B.)
$C \times 10^6$	32.0	26.35	20.05	2.85	0.75

In the above table the letters (S. P. B) indicate the sample prepared from sulphate by precipitation. An aqueous suspension of this sample was exposed in the absence of phenol and as such serves as a blank.

TABLE IX

ZnO (0.2 g.), conductivity water (30 c.c.), and glycerol (0.1M) exposed in open pyrex flasks to sunlight for 5 hours.

ZnO	(C.I.)	(S.P.)	(N.P.)	(N.I.)
$C \times 10^6$	17.60	10.55	2.5	1.35

These results indicate that zinc oxide prepared from carbonate by ignition has the greatest activity, while the oxide prepared from the nitrate by ignition is the least active. The activities of the other two samples lie between these two extremes. The relatively low activity of the sample prepared from nitrate by ignition is probably due to the presence of adsorbed oxides of nitrogen which lends colour to the sample. This point will be referred to in the discussion.

D I S C U S S I O N

The photochemical formation of hydrogen peroxide from water in contact with air takes place in sunlight as well as in artificial ultraviolet and visible light in the presence of zinc oxide.

The yield of hydrogen peroxide increases in the presence of some organic compounds such as phenol, glycerol, acetanilide, ethyl alcohol, ether, acetone, benzidine, salicylic acid and oxalic acid. No hydrogen peroxide was, however, detected when aqueous solutions of these substances were exposed to light in blank experiments in the absence of zinc oxide, which shows that these substances either take an active part in the process of the formation of hydrogen peroxide through zinc oxide or they simply help in stabilising hydrogen peroxide formed in the process, or act in both ways. The part played by these substance in the reaction will be discussed in a subsequent communication.

From a study of the photosensitisation by zinc oxide in monochromatic light, secured by means of light filters, it was found that some hydrogen peroxide was also formed in the

violet region of the visible spectrum (400-470 $m\mu$). This indicates that the photosensitive range of zinc oxide extends up to the violet. Goodeve (*loc. cit.*) from a study of the diffuse reflection spectra of zinc oxide determined the position of its absorption band. There was a sharp fall in the reflecting power of the powder at 385 $m\mu$, indicating the entry of a strong absorption band with a fairly sharp threshold at the wave-length. Hence it was concluded that zinc oxide absorbs in the near ultraviolet, which is exactly the region in which the oxide is found to be photo-active. But our results show that the photo-active range of zinc oxide and consequently its absorption extends even up to the violet *i.e.*, 435 $m\mu$.

Of all the four samples of zinc oxide tried, the one prepared from carbonate by ignition was found to possess the greatest activity. Richards and Rogers (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1893, 15, 567) have shown that zinc oxide prepared by the ignition of the carbonate always carries occluded gases which mainly consist of carbon dioxide and oxygen. It is also well known that zinc oxide adsorbs carbon dioxide from the air. These observations led the present authors to the idea that zinc carbonate itself might also sensitise the reaction. Preliminary experiments tried with zinc carbonate powder confirmed the idea. Detailed quantitative study of zinc carbonate as a sensitiser in this reaction will form the subject matter of a later paper.

Zinc oxide prepared from nitrate by ignition was found to be the least active of all the samples tried. The greenish yellow colour of the sample has been shown to be due to the occlusion of oxides of nitrogen. The lower yield of hydrogen peroxide with the sample might be explained as being due to the partial destruction of hydrogen peroxide formed during the reaction by the nitrite present in the system.

Further work directed towards the elucidation of the mechanism of this reaction is in progress.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
OSMANIA UNIVERSITY,
HYDERABAD, DECCAN.

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